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Minimizing Miss Ratio Using Modified Cache Memory Replacement Algorithm (M-CAR)

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Abstract

Through taking advantage of locality in memory accesses, caching can be defined as a fundamental approach frequently used for hiding the latency gap between Central Processing Unit (CPU) and Main Memory (MM). In order to decide which blocks to remove from the cache memory in the event of the cache miss, various cache replacement methods are used, each of which has significantly distinctive influence on system performance. Through making the best use of cache's entire size, reducing miss ratio as much as it is feasible, and obtaining maximum system performance possible, such replacement approaches strive to move closer to the ideal scenario. A modified approach called (M-CAR) will be introduced in this study using the clock with adaptive replacement algorithm (CAR), which delivers a greater hit ratio compared to conventional method.

Keywords: Cache Memory; Cache Miss; Replacement Algorithms; Cache Hit; M-CAR

1. Introduction

To close the gap between memory access time and CPU performance speed, cache memory was developed. Even while modern memory technology can't convey, the computer CPU runs at a high speed, leading to an issue known as the wait state. A wait state, which is experienced via a computer processor in the case of accessing an external memory or any device which has slow response, is only an additional clock cycle to give certain device the time that is needed for completing a process [1]. During this delay, the CPU is unable to perform any data on the data it is waiting for from memory. M. V. Wilkes created cache memory in 1965. At that time, Wilkes referred to cache memory as "slave memory" and described it as the second level of a high-speed unconventional memory which produces a 0-wait state [2].

Cache memory is a fast, extremely small, 0-wait state memory, placed between M.M and CPU to act as a bridge that exchange and store data. Due to the small size of this memory, a major problem in cache memory is the so-called "cache miss". A cache miss occurs if the CPU requests an item of data that is not available in the cache. Otherwise, a "cache hit" occurs if the CPU requests an item of data that is available in the cache [3, 4]. If a cache miss occurs, a replacement policy is required if the space required to load the memory blocks is not available in the cache. M.M is going to be searched for that item and transfers it to the cache, and a decision must be made to swap blocks. These steps are made by the replacement algorithms [2, 3] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cache and M.M Data Transfer.

2. Replacement Algorithms

In the case where cache miss takes place and there's nowhere in the cache to load memory blocks, replacement algorithms are required. The replacement algorithm needs to be carried out in hardware for operating at high speed. The present block in the cache is chosen by a replacement algorithm. Several of such algorithms include [3]:

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2.1. Optimal

The block which will not be required the most in future is replaced using this algorithm. Although this policy of replacement isn't feasible, it is frequently utilized as a benchmark to assess how effective other replacement plans are.

2.2. Random

This algorithm might choose cache block for the replacements in completely arbitrary order while ignoring memory references.

2.3. First-In, First-Out (FIFO)

In the case when a cache block needs to be replaced, this algorithm selects oldest available block.

2.4. Least Recently Used (LRU)

This technique is based upon an idea that in the case where a block has recently been referred, it may do so again in the future. In other words, it is likely that a block that has just been referenced will be referenced once more.

2.5. Least-Frequently-Used (LFU)

In a case when an eviction is necessary, this method uses the software counter related to each cache block to replace the block that is utilized the least often.

3. Methodology

There are several researches which resulted in inventing and developing some of the advanced cache replacement approaches which minimizing the miss ratio and reducing speed disparity between CPU and M.M access time such as:

3.1. CLOCK Algorithm

This must be structured in a circular list representing the page. The hand of the clock has been applied to point to the buffer's oldest data page. Every data page has associated reference bit that is fixed in an event where certain data page was referenced. Cache replacement policy is going to be invoked if there's a page fault, where data page is pointed to by hand (which inspects oldest data page) [2]. In an event where setting reference bit of data page, then, the bit will be reset to the value of 0; in addition to that, the next oldest data page is pointed to by hand. This kind of the process will be continued to the point where data page with reference bit of 0 has been found. Which is why, the data page will be taken away from the buffer; a new data page will be inserted instead of it whereas reference bit is set to the value of 0 [4].

The disadvantages of this technique are:

- Not practical (evicted block may be needed in a short time later).
- Not scan resistant (this makes this technique slow).
- Low hit ratio (in case of unrepeated sequence of data pages).

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3.2. Dueling CLOCK

This represents a policy of adaptive replacement that functions based upon CLOCK method. For purposes of achievement of the CLOCK scan-resistant, single necessary modification is that hand of clock has to point to the buffer's latest data page rather than the oldest one [5]. It might be viewed as a method of the adaptive replacements using CLOCK structure. The cache will be split to 3 groups, which are: (M1), (M2) and (M3). This algorithm is constantly implemented as a substitution approach for a small set of (M1), whereas scan-resistant CLOCK is going to be utilized always by small sets (M2 and M3), which are the large sets may be applied between the scan-resistant CLOCK and the CLOCK, according to the comparative performance that is associated with the two former sets. For specifying policy of replacement which must be applied for (M3), (10-bit) policy select counter (PSEL) is going to be carried out [5,6].

The disadvantages of this technique are:

- Efficient performance only when applied in multi-level caches (level 2 precisely).
- Technical complexity.
- Low hit ratio (when data pages resides in level 1 or level 3).

3.3. CLOCK-Pro

CLOCK-Pro algorithm attempts to utilize CLOCK for the approximation of the reuse distance. In a case of the access to some certain page, this page will be viewed as "hot" if it has little reuse distance, whereas it will be viewed as "cold" page in a case where it has a massive reuse distance. The pages are accessed in a list in which pages that have small level of the regency will be placed at head of the list, whereas the pages that have a larger level of the regency will be placed at end of that list. The circular list is utilized in order to keep entries of the cache page [6, 7]. There are three status bits that are associated with these pages; cold or hot indicator, referencing bit, and indicator for every one of the cold pages that might specify whether or not a page is in the test phase. The CLOCK-Pro approach has 3-hands. The HAND cold has been viewed as the first one that points to the last resident cold page, or cold page that is substituted after that. Over the process of the page substitution, the page which is chosen via the HAND cold will be evicted in an event where the reference bit that is associated with the page is 0. Hand-hot is the 2nd hand pointing to hot page with the maximum regency. In a case where reference bit that is associated with the page which has been chosen by Hand-hot is 0, the page becomes considered to be a cold page [6,8].

The disadvantages of this technique are:

- Mathematical complexity.
- Captures only 'regency' factor.

In addition to the previous techniques, Clock with Adaptive Replacement (CAR) is one of the advanced algorithms in cache memory replacement field and it will be explained in detail because its parameters, ideas and features will be the inspiration to the suggested approach of the present paper.

4. Clock with Adaptive Replacement (CAR)

T2, T1, B2, and B1 are the four linked lists that make up the CAR directory. Link lists T2 and T1 as CLOCK policy implementers and B2 and B1 as LRU policy implementers. CAR directory structure is depicted in the **Figure 2**[6, 7].

Lists B2 and B1 include history pages which have lately been evicted from the cache, and CLOCKS T2 and T1 contain such pages which are now in the cache. While the CLOCK T2 records Frequency (F), the CLOCK T1 records regency (R). Simple LRU lists can be found in lists B2 and B1. Pages that have been evicted from T1 have been placed upon B1, and the ones that have been removed from T2 were placed on B2. This algorithm aims to maintain B2 and B1 at nearly equivalent sizes to T2 and T1 respectively. Additionally, the technique prevents $|T1| + |B1|$ from going above the cache size. In response to a varying workload, the sizes regarding the CLOCKS T2 and T1 are continuously adjusted. T1 target size is increased anytime a hit in B1 has been detected; conversely, target T1 size has been decreased whenever a hit in the B2 has been detected. The new pages have been placed in T2 or T1, directly behind hands of the clock that have been displayed in order to move in a clockwise direction. New pages have a page reference bit that has been set to "0" [8, 9] (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. CAR Directory Structure.

Any page in T1 U T2 can be cached by setting the page reference bit for that page to "1". T1 clock hand moves page behind T2 clock hand then resets reference bit of the page to value of "0" in the case where it meets a page that has page reference bit of "1". A "0-page" reference bit page is evicted then put at the Most Recently Used position (MRU) in the B1 whenever T1 clock hand comes across it. Page reference bit is reset to the value of "0" if T2 clock hand comes across page with page reference bit that equals "1". A page that has been evicted then placed at the MRU position in the B2 any time where T2 clock hand comes into contact with one [10, 11].

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4.1. CAR algorithm

The basic CAR algorithm is the following [4, 5, 9]

INITIALIZATIONS: Set $p = 0$ and set lists T1, B1, B2 and T2 as empty.

CAR(x)

INPUT: requested page x.

if (x is in T2 U T1) then

/* cacheHit */

Set page reference bit for x to the value of 1.

otherwise /* cacheMiss */ if $(|T2| + |T1| = c)$

/* cacheFull, substitute page from the cache */

replace()

/* replacement of the directory of the cache */

if $(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1) \text{ and } (|B1| + |T1| = c)$

Discarding the LRU page in the B1.

Else if $(|T1| + |B1| + |T2| + |B2| = 2c) \text{ and } (x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$

Discarding the LRU page in the B2.

End if

End if

/* cache the directory miss */

if $(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$ then

Insert x at T1 tail. Set the reference bit of page of x to 0.

4.2. Disadvantages of CAR

The disadvantages of CAR are that it does not handle temporal filtering. So, it must be imposing more stringent separation between short-term and long-term utility pages for specific workloads. This means that Regency (R) and Frequency (F) could not select the best candidate data page for eviction, which results in a lower hit ratio [12, 13].

5. The Proposed Modification (M-Car)

The proposed technique will concentrate on giving greater importance to the Frequency Factor (F) in specific conditions during requesting a new data pages and cache is full. Normally, in traditional CAR algorithm, when a cache miss occurs, a data page will be evicted from T2 (meaning that it was frequently utilized prior to being evicted from cache). Thus, the proposed modification will be this:

- When cache miss occurs in T2, if coincides with the fact that the data block in the tail of T2 is MAXF then the data block with MAXF-1 will be evicted from T2 and placed at the Most Recently Used position (MRU) in B2.
- When a cache miss occurs in B2, the data block will be evicted out of cache from B2 will not be the data block with MAXF even if it was at the end of B2 list but the data block that positioned before the Most Recently Used position (MRU-1) in B2 will be moved out of cache.

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5.1. M-CAR Algorithm

INITIALIZATIONS: Set $p = 0$ and lists $T1$, $B1$, $B2$ and $T2$ to empty.

CAR(x)

INPUT: requested page x.

if (x is in $T2 \cup T1$) /* cacheHit */

Set reference bit of page for x to the value of 1.

Otherwise /* cacheMiss in T 2 */

if ($|T2| + |T1| = c$)

/* cache full, substitute page from the cache */

replace()

/* replacement of the cache directory */

if ($(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$ and $(|B1| + |T1| = c)$) and LRU page is MAXF

Discard MAXF-1 page in the B 2.

Else if ($(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$ and $(|B1| + |T1| = c)$) then

Discard LRU page in the B 1.

Else if ($(|T1| + |B1| + |T2| + |B2| = 2c)$ and $(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$) then

Discard LRU page in the B 2.

End if

End if

End if

/* cache directory miss */

if ($(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$ and $(|B1| + |T1| = c)$) and page of MRU is MAXF

Discard MRU-1 page in the B 2.

Else if $(x \text{ isn't in } B2 \cup B1)$

Insert x at T1 tail. Set reference bit of the page of x to 0.

6. Implementation & Results

The criteria of the efficiency that have been utilized for the judgement of performance of the proposed algorithm will be the hit ratio gained by (M-CAR) and original (CAR) because cache memory was basically invented to solve the wait state problem by keeping useful data block to achieve the highest hit ratio can be reached 9 (Figures 3, 4).

These algorithms will operate on the same set of input files (data sets). Additionally, using equation, the hit ratio, which is presented as the program's final findings, will be used to measure the performance of the cache:

$$\text{hit ratio \%} = \frac{\text{No. of cache hits}}{\text{No. of memory references in data set}} * 100$$

It should be indicated that the records containing failed tests will be coloured with light grey.

Dataset-1:

Which contains (206) items

{2, 3, 4, 1, 2, 4, 140, 150, 3, 2, 1, 4, 6, 5, 170, 180, 190, 200, 5, 6, 1, 7, 3, 4, 2, 5, 6, 7, 4, 210, 220, 1, 3, 5, 7, 2, 4, 6, 1, 8, 6, 7, 2, 3, 4, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 230, 240, 250, 260, 270, 280, 290, 300, 7, 8, 1, 3, 5, 6, 2, 4, 1, 8, 6, 310, 320, 330, 340,

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350, 1, 8, 7, 2, 4, 3, 8, 6, 5, 7, 1, 360, 370, 380, 390, 400, 410, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 6, 1, 15, 2, 3, 15, 17, 16, 4, 17, 16, 7, 6, 1, 5, 15, 17, 8, 5, 21, 16, 15, 17, 2, 3, 16, 21, 17, 15, 16, 4, 7, 6, 7, 3, 2, 17, 21, 23, 24, 8, 15, 12, 17, 19, 21, 16, 4, 1, 2, 3, 8, 19, 8, 7, 6, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 19, 18, 17, 16, 2, 13, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 21, 22, 18, 16, 14, 12, 2, 4, 6, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 9, 6, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1}

The next results were obtained:

Table 1. CAR vs. M-CAR for dataset-1.

Cache size	CAR Hit Ratio (%)	M-CAR hit ratio (%)
7	41.03	41.88
8	43.06	44.53
9	46.15	46.01
10	48.18	50.9
11	48.18	54.5
12	51.09	50.12
13	51.4	52.42
14	52.66	51.99
15	52.97	53.72
16	57.08	61.33

Figure 3. CAR vs. M-CAR chart for Data set-1 Dataset-2.

Which contains (203) items

{1, 5, 15, 17, 8, 5, 21, 16, 15, 17, 2, 3, 16, 21, 17, 15, 16, 4, 7, 6, 7, 3, 2, 17, 21, 23, 24, 8, 15, 12, 17, 19, 21, 16, 4, 1, 2, 3, 8, 19, 8, 7, 6, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 19, 18, 17, 16, 2, 13, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 21, 22, 18, 16, 14, 12, 2, 4, 6, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 9, 6, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 100, 110, 120, 130, 1, 2, 3, 4, 1, 2, 4, 140, 150, 3,

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2, 1, 4, 6, 5, 170, 180, 190, 200, 5, 6, 1, 7, 3, 4, 2, 5, 6, 7, 4, 210, 220, 1, 3, 5, 7, 2, 4, 6, 1, 8, 6, 7, 2, 3, 4, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 230, 240, 250, 260, 270, 280, 290, 300, 7, 8, 1, 3, 5, 6, 2, 4, 1, 8, 6, 310, 320, 330, 340, 350, 1, 8, 7, 2, 4, 3, 8, 6, 5, 7, 1, 360, 370, 380, 390, 400, 410, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 6, 1, 15, 2, 3}

The results below have been obtained:

Table 2. CAR vs. M-CAR for Dataset-2.

Cache size	CAR hit ratio (%)	M-CAR hit ratio (%)
7	34.95	35.22
8	36.01	36.74
9	39.81	42.03
10	39.5	41.52
11	47.43	45.16
12	48.54	49.66
13	56.31	57
14	61.17	62.78
15	62.77	62.78
16	62.03	63.5

Figure 4. CAR vs. M-CAR chart for Data set-2.

7. Discussion

Based on the results in **Table 1**, (M-CAR) has obtained higher hit ratio comparing to (CAR) with a percentage of (70%). And based on the results in **Table 2**, (M-CAR) has obtained higher hit ratio comparing to (CAR) with a percentage of (90%). This means that, as a final conclusion for both **Table 1** and **Table 2**, (M-CAR) has obtained higher hit ratio comparing to (CAR) with a percentage of (80 %). which means, by default, that M-CAR has succeeded in minimizing miss ratio.

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8. Conclusion

Finally, it is recommended that the basic technique (CAR) can be developed by using ideas and best features from Low Inter-Reference Regency Set technique (LIRS) to obtain higher hit ratio.

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